

Effects of Land-Use Land-Cover Change on River flow in Chalimbana River Catchment, Chongwe District, Zambia

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Abstract:- Land-use land-cover changes due to anthropogenic activities resulting from rapid population increase are among the factors that have changed the hydrological response of most catchments in Zambia. Therefore, understanding its impacts will help in coming up with sustainable strategies that will preserve and sustain the catchments. The objective of this research was to analyze the effects of land-use land-cover change on riverflow in Chalimbana river catchment. This study analyzed, spatially, the impact of land use changes from the year 1980 to 2020. Remote sensing and GIS related soft wares were used to analyze the Landsat images; riverflow and rainfall data for the period 1980 to 2020 was analyzed using linear regression and trend analysis with the help of Xlstat (in excel) and Minitab soft wares. The results showed that there has been significant land-use and land cover change in the Chalimbana catchment where the forest and vegetation cover which occupied 57.48 percent in 1980, decreased to 28.14 percent in 2020. The area occupied by agriculture and grassland increased from 34.54 percent in 1980 to 56.5 percent in 2020. There was also an increase in built-up area from 7.9 percent in 1980 to 15.0 percent in 2020 and water bodies increased from 0.08 per cent in 1980 to 0.36 per cent in 2020. The study also revealed that streamflow increased from 14.49 m³/s in 1980 to 94.4 m³/s in 2020. It was observed that the increase in built-up area as well as in agricultural activities have significantly contributed to this increase in riverflow.

Keywords:- Land-use land-cover change; riverflow; GIS; Chalimbana catchment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid changes in land use/cover have characterised Lusaka province over the past 4 decades. This has been due to urbanization which has resulted to clearance of significant amounts of forests and vegetation cover resulting to various land use changes. This rampant urban growth and loss of natural vegetation cover have led to increased environmental degradation activities (such as sand mining and harvesting, intermittent cutting down of trees, etc.) in Lusaka, due to increased demand for construction materials[1]. The increase in the number of people (due to increase in population of Lusaka city) over the past decades in the Chalimbana catchment have impacted negatively on the environment. The impacts have been reflected on the use of the natural resources such as water and land. The two natural resources are driven by economic and political

structures existing in the country as well as social values and norms of the surrounding society[1]. This has been exacerbated by lack of appropriate land use planning and inadequate sustainable development measures [2], [3]. Chalimbana catchment in Chongwe district of Lusaka province is one of the regions where depletion of the natural vegetation has seemingly resulted to the drying up of the Chalimbana river whose recharge zone is the famous forest number 27. The Chalimbana sub-catchment has been deforested heavily and most of the local communities believe that this could be the main contributing factor to the drying up of the Chalimbana River [4]. This has not only affected the resident farmers of the catchment who depend on this river for farming, but has also disturbed the hydrological response of the river resulting to hydrologic regime change [5]. Therefore, there is need for urgent and quick action to save the remaining part of the catchment. The effect of LULC on riverflow, and the consequent land degradation, is one of the most important environmental problems faced in many river catchments [6]. Hence, it is imperative to evaluate the magnitude, pattern and type of land use/cover changes. Such data will help in coming up with sustainable ways of managing the catchment. Against this background, this study assessed the effects of land use/cover changes on streamflow in Chalimbana river catchment from 1980 to 2020.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The Study Area

The Chalimbana river catchment is a sub-catchment of the Chongwe catchment which lies within the Zambezi river basin. The catchment lies Northeast to Southeast of the city of Lusaka and is readily accessible via the State Lodge road in Lusaka East or the Great East Road. The river, with length of about 37 km, has a number of perennial and non-perennial tributaries draining into it before it finally drains into the Chongwe River. It is located between latitude 15° 20' S to 15° 32' S and longitude 28°22' E to 28°44' E. The catchment extends from the eastern periphery of Lusaka district into Chongwe district to the east of Lusaka. The catchment has an area of approximately 644.5 km²[4], [7]. Chalimbana sub-catchment is located in ecological region-IIa where the mean annual rainfall ranges between 200 mm and 1000 mm. This region has three main seasons namely, cool-dry from May to August, hot and dry from September to October and the hot-wet from November to April. Average mean daily temperatures range from 23- 26 degrees Celsius in the hottest month of October to 16-20 degrees Celsius in the coldest months of June and July. The most

common soils in Region IIa are red to brown clayey to loamy soil types that are moderately to strongly leached. Physical characteristics of the soils that affect crop production, include low water holding capacity, shallow rooting depth, and top soils prone to rapid deterioration and erosion. Two main soil types are identifiable in the catchment. The dominant being the Leptosols which are very shallow, extremely stony or gravelly and well-drained soils, prevail in the hilly areas of the catchment to the East and along the escarpment to the south of Chongwe [7],[8], [9].

The Chalimbana River Catchment is mainly covered by the Miombo Woodlands. It is dominated by semi-evergreen trees (predominantly *Brachystegia* and *Isoberlinia* species) 15 to 21 meters high with a well-developed grass layer under an open or partially closed canopy [10], [11]. The Geology of the upper part of the Chalimbana river basin

is characterized by three rock types: Chlorite (Muscovite, Quartz and Muscovite Schist), crystalline dolomitic limestone and Quartz (Muscovite and Biotite Schist). The catchment has an undulating terrain with an altitude ranging from 1029 to 1342 meters above sea level. The dissected cretaceous surface gives the Chalimbana headwaters region its present hilly topography [10].

The Catchment is drained by the Chalimbana River, which has its source in Forest Reserves No. 27 South-east of the City of Lusaka, near Bauleni Compound. It flows eastwards to its confluence with the Chongwe River. The river has several recharge tributaries flowing into it from the northerly and southerly directions, which include Mukamunye, Kapwelyomba, Kashikili, Buyuni and Njolwe [4].Figure 1 shows the location and hydrology of Chalimbana catchment.

Fig. 1: Location of Chalimbana catchment and its hydrologic make-up

Source: Researcher (2021)

B. Data Collection

In this study, data collection involved downloading and processing Landsat images for the study area for the years 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020; collection of raw streamflow data from WARMA and collection of daily/monthly/annual rainfall data from Zambia Meteorological Department and SASSCAL website.

a) Landsat data

The study used Satellite images from Landsat-7 and Landsat-8 Operation Land Imager for mapping the land uses and detecting changes. The images selected were those with less than 10% cloud cover. Landsat images for the year 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 were downloaded from USGS website (USGS Earth Explorer) under the link <http://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>. The image specifications before processing are as indicated in table 1 below:

Satellite Image	Resolution (m)	Sensor	Path	Row	Year	Cloud cover
Landsat 8	30 X 30	TM	169	52	2020	Less than 10 percent
Landsat 7	30 X 30	TM	169	52	2010	Less than 10 percent
Landsat 7	30 X 30	TM	169	52	2000	Less than 10 percent
Landsat 7	30 X 30	TM	169	52	1990	Less than 10 percent
Landsat 7	30 X 30	TM	169	52	1980	Less than 10 percent

Table 1: Satellite image specifications used

The temporal and spatial variation in land use within Chalimbana River sub-catchment from 1980 to 2020 was collected from the satellite imageries for land use/cover change for the years 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 downloaded from the United States Geological Survey website (<http://earthexplore.usgs.gov>). The Chalimbana Landsat imageries were interpreted to ascertain land-use land-cover changes over the time period using ArcGIS 10.4.1 software. This method was used in looking at dynamics of land use/cover changes and degradation of Nairobi City [12]. This method when looking at the effects of land use change on stream flow, channel erosion and river geomorphology of Motoine/Ngong river sub-catchment, Nairobi river basin in Kenya[13].

• Accuracy Assessment

Accuracy assessment determines the quality of a map created from remotely sensed data [14]. This study used the quantitative accuracy assessment whose goal was to identify and measure map errors so that the map can be as useful as possible to the persons who would be using it to make decisions. Accuracy assessment was done using Google Earth as the ground truth reference. Fifty ground control points for each LULC type (except for water bodies which had 30 due to its size) were plotted on the classified images which were then converted into KML (keyhole mark-up language) and opened in Google earth (as reference points) for respective years. The ground control points (180 in total for each map) were sampled using stratified random sampling, where the number of points was stratified to the land use/land cover types. Kappa coefficient was also used in assessing the accuracy of the classification, as it is a potent indicator of the accuracy estimation for the LULC map. By allowing the reference pixels to be selected at random, the possibility of bias is lessened. Accuracy assessment was measured through an error matrix using user classification and reference image. An error matrix is a very effective way of representing thematic map accuracy, because it provides a clear way of deriving the individual accuracies of each class along with both the errors of inclusion (commission errors) and errors of exclusion (omission errors) present in the classification[15].

Generally, all the maps met the minimum USGS accuracy requirements (minimum overall interpretation accuracy of at least 85 per cent) as stipulated by the Anderson classification scheme [16]. The overall map accuracies were 85%, 87%, 90%, 92% and 89% for 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 maps respectively.

b) Streamflow

Streamflow data for the period 1980 to 2020 was collected from Water Resources Management Authority (WARMA)

for Romar gauging point. To eliminate the rainfall factor from streamflow, the monthly/annual rainfall data for the period 1980 to 2020 was used. The rainfall data was obtained from the Zambia Meteorological Department and SASSCAL website.

C. Data Analysis

Data analysis involved processing and reprocessing of satellite images, supervised and unsupervised classification and accuracy assessment of produced land-use maps. Raw rainfall and streamflow data were converted to mean monthly/annual, percentages, graphical as well as tabular form for easy visualization and analysis of the data.

• Land-use Land-cover Data

The downloaded Landsat imageries were subjected to a supervised and unsupervised classification processes. The supervised classification was done under four classes namely: agriculture/grassland, built-up area, and forest/vegetation and water bodies. Water bodies included rivers, dams, ponds, and other water reservoirs. Built-up area included buildings, bare land, and roads, playing grounds, airport and other infrastructure. Agriculture/Grassland included farming areas (both irrigated and rain fed), grassland and sparsely shrubs. Forest/Vegetation cover included forested areas with both artificial and exotic species which are both sparsely and thick forested areas as well as dense shrubs. This classification criterion was partly based on the observed features, literature reviewed and the Land Classification Scheme by Anderson and others[16].

The unsupervised classification was first done under 12 classes, which were later reclassified into the four classes stated above. The aim of first classifying the Landsat imageries into 12 classes was to ensure that the software brings out or classifies most of the visible/recognizable differences into different classes without being restricted. The Chalimbana River sub-catchment was then extracted, by masking, from the classified Landsat imagery using the shape file of the catchment boundary which was delineated from the downloaded digital elevation model (DEM) of the study area using the masking tool in ArcMap. The LULC maps were then subjected to an accuracy assessment after which vectorization was performed in ArcGIS. This facilitated the calculation of the areas at a 10-year interval for the specified land use/land cover classes for the years 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 as presented in table 4.1 in the next chapter. This operation was made possible by a field calculator tool in the table of content window in ArcMap. The areas were presented in square kilometers and

percentages. The purpose here was to determine the temporal and spatial land use changes within the catchment.

- Streamflow and Rainfall

The daily stream flow and rainfall data were converted to mean monthly data respectively. The mean rainfall and mean streamflow were then compared for the purpose of determining whether there is a relationship between rainfall and streamflow. Furthermore, the respective decadal LULC areas were compared with the decadal streamflow for the purpose of determining variability in streamflow with changes in land use. These comparisons were done by performing a correlation between mean streamflow and LULC type as well as mean rainfall.

III. RESULTS

A. Land-use Land-cover dynamics in Chalimbana catchment 1980-2020

This study found that there have been significant changes in the LULC types in Chalimbana catchment from 1980 to 2020. The classified and assessed LULC maps for Chalimbana catchment for the years 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 are presented in figure 3. The total area coverage of the Chalimbana catchment, calculated in ArcMap 10.4.1, was found to be approximately 644.5 km². Table 2 presents the findings of the LULC area changes at a ten-year interval and the mean change of each LULC type over the period 1980 to 2020. The purpose here was to determine the temporal and spatial land-use land-cover changes within the catchment from over the period under review.

a) Forest and Vegetation cover

As shown in table 2, forest and vegetation cover has been decreasing significantly from 1980 to 2020 with the greatest decrease (10.1 percent) being between 2010 and 2020 representing a mean decrease of 7.33 percent of the total catchment area. This observed decrease can be attributed, partly, to the partial degazetting of forest number 27 (a significant forest area in the catchment area) to farm and settlement land. In 2017, 67 hectares of this forest land was excised; in 2018, 504 hectares was excised; in 2019, 477 hectares was excised and 110 hectares was planned for residential and mixed use. This was necessitated by the developmental needs due to increase in population of Lusaka city and the surrounding districts such as Chongwe and Chibombo [17]. This resulted to an intermittent clearance of the forest area and other parts of the catchment for construction of housing units, roads, and other infrastructure. Furthermore, apart from conversion of forest land to built-up area and farmland, the decrease in forest land can be attributed to the high demand for forest products such as wood products and charcoal production. Forest/vegetation cover in Chalimbana catchment has been decreasing at the rate of 4.73 km²/year. [18] in their study of transportation and distribution of charcoal to Lusaka city markets found that 36 percent of the consumption of Charcoal supplied in Lusaka City comes from Chongwe River Catchment. This increase in demand for forest products is a result of massive socio-economic activities and urbanization in the Chongwe River Catchment to which Chalimbana is a sub-catchment [18]. Some of the key root

causes of the indiscriminate destruction of the natural resources and environmental degradation in Chongwe catchment are increases in the demand for food and energy for the urban population [19].

b) Built-up Area

Built-up area decreased by 0.4 percent and 4.3 percent from 1980 to 1990 and from 2000 to 2010 respectively, while it increased by 10 percent and 1.4 percent from 1990 to 2000 and 2010 to 2020 respectively. As shown in table 4.1, this represents a mean increase of 1.77 percent. This implies that, on average, built-up area has been increasing at the rate of 1.14 km²/year from 1980 to 2020. The increase in built-up area resulted to increased demand for construction materials, such as sand and crushed stones, thereby resulting to increased land degradation activities such as sand mining which characterize most areas in the outskirts of Lusaka city. The increase in the built-up area can be attributed mainly to the radial expansion of Lusaka City and the surrounding areas. This is expected to continue as the urbanization and the overall socio-economic development activities in Lusaka City, Chongwe and Chisamba towns continue to increase.

Fig. 3: Land-use Land-cover changes in chalimbana from 1980-2020

Source: Field Data (2021)

Table 2: Land use/cover types and changes in a 10-year interval

LULC type	1980		1990		2000		2010		2020		Mean area change (km ²)
	Area (km ²)	Area (km ²)	Area change (1980-1990) (km ²)	Area (km ²)	Area change (1990-2000) (km ²)	Area (km ²)	Area change (2000-2010) (km ²)	Area (km ²)	Area change (2010-2020) (km ²)		
AG	222.62	280.49	57.87	258.61	-21.88	308.27	49.66	364.17	55.9	35.39	
BA	50.91	48.52	-2.39	115.46	66.94	87.34	-28.12	96.62	9.28	11.43	
FV	370.51	314.33	-56.18	268.17	-46.16	246.52	-21.65	181.37	-65.15	-47.29	
WB	0.46	1.16	0.7	2.26	1.1	2.37	0.11	2.34	-0.03	0.47	
Total	644.5	644.5	0	644.5	0	644.5	0	644.5	0	0	

Where, AG = agriculture/grassland, BA = builtup area, FV = forest/vegetation, and WB = water bodies.

Source: Research data (2021).

c) Agricultural and Grassland

The catchment has, for the past forty years, experienced an increase in Agricultural/grassland from 222.62 km² in 1980 to 364.17 km² in 2020, representing 21.96 percentage increase. This represents a mean increase of 5.49 percent. However, between 1990 and 2000 agriculture and grassland decreased by 3.39 percent (21.88 km²). Generally, agriculture and grassland area has been increasing at the rate of 3.54 km²/ year between 1980 and 2020 representing an increase of 21.96 percent of the total catchment area. This increment is attributed to an increase in farming activities in most parts of the Chalimbana River Catchment. The farmland has been increasing at the expense of forest and vegetation land. This increase is as a result of the decrease in forest and vegetation cover as much of the forest areas have been converted to agriculture area. This has been shown by the continuous decrease in forest cover from 1980 to 2020.

d) Water Bodies

As can be noticed from table 2, area coverage of water bodies in Chalimbana sub-catchment have been increasing at a rate of 0.047 km²/year between 1980 and 2020 representing an increase change of 0.29 percent of the total catchment area. Similar studies by Mishra and others found that water bodies increased by 0.11 percent (0.28 km²) between 1988 and 2017 in assessing Land use and land cover change detection in the Sikkim Himalaya, India[20]. Similar results were found in River Ruiru watershed in Kenya in which water bodies increased from 1257 hectares in 1984 to 1810 hectares in 2017 [21]. Though not very significant, this increase in surface water coverage in Chalimbana catchment can be attributed to the increase in water reservoirs in the catchment such as dams for irrigated farming by both commercial and small-scale farmers. Chalimbana River has been impounded by a number of farmers who have been using the trapped water for irrigation. This has resulted in an increase in water abstraction in the catchment. This has its negative consequences in terms of water distribution in the catchment. According to [3], over abstraction of water from natural bodies and wetlands leads to drying up of the water bodies. However, [3] found that water bodies were

decreasing in the Chongwe catchment in which the Chalimbana is a sub-catchment. The difference could be due to the fact that in small catchments such as Chalimbana, there are few factors that contribute to the change in the hydrological regime as compared to large catchments, like Chongwe, which have many factors to be considered such as climate change, evapotranspiration, LULC change, soil characteristics, vegetation types and density, and many more.

• Implications of Land-use land-cover changes

During the field survey of some parts of the catchment, it was observed that deforestation, soil erosion, sedimentation and siltation were the main hydro-geomorphological processes occurring in the catchment and in particular along the Chalimbana river, thereby making the river shallow. It was further observed that gardening and farming along the river banks were a common practice. This has led to the filling up of some parts of the river as loose sediments from cultivated areas and other bare lands are easily carried away and deposited into the river. Furthermore, the application of fertiliser which is, in turn, washed away into the river is a potential source of contamination of water in the river.

B. Effects of LULC change on streamflow in Chalimbana catchment

The daily streamflow and rainfall data were converted to mean monthly data respectively. Then a comparison between land use and river discharge was made with the purpose of determining the variability in streamflow with changes in land use/land cover. Table 3 compares decadal mean streamflow with decadal mean rainfall over the period 1980 to 2020. There have been minimal variations in terms of decadal mean annual rainfall (from 76.1 mm in 1980 to 76.7 mm, 68.3 mm, 85.3 mm and 80.3 mm in 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 respectively). The catchment received the lowest mean decadal rainfall in 2000 (68.3 mm) and the highest in 2010 (85.3 mm). Thus, rainfall has been increasing at the rate of 1.05 mm per decade. The observed variations in rainfall implies that the pattern of rainfall received in the region has not significantly changed over the period of study. The observed changes could be attributed to normal rainfall variability from season to season.

	Year				
	1980	1990	2000	2010	2020
Mean stream flow (m ³ /sec)	14.49	2.814	46.941	78.58	94.4
Change in mean stream flow	N/A	-11.676	44.127	31.639	15.82
Mean annual rain fall (mm)	76.1	76.7	68.3	85.3	80.3

Table 3: Decadal mean Streamflow data for the period 1980 to 2020

Source: Research data (2021)

From table 3, it can be observed that Chalimbana River, at Romor gauging point, recorded increased mean decadal streamflow of 14.49 m³/s, 46.94 m³/s, 78.58 m³/s and 94.4 m³/s in 1980, 2000, 2010 and 2020 respectively. In 1990, the river recorded the lowest mean decadal streamflow (2.814 m³/s) and the highest being in 2020 (94.4 m³/s). Streamflow has been increasing at the rate of 19.98 m³/s per decade. The observed decrease in streamflow between 1980 and 1990 can be attributed to the increase in

agriculture/grassland during the same period. The area under agriculture increased by the largest percentage (10 percent) during this period compared to the increase in the other years. It can further be observed that between 1990 and 2000, the highest increase in streamflow (44.127 m³/s) was recorded compared to the increase recorded in the other years. This can be attributed to the increase in built-up area during the same period. Rainfall satisfies the soil moisture deficit in agricultural area more quickly than in forested

areas thereby generating more runoff. Furthermore, forest cover intercepts rainfall and increases infiltration opportunity time thereby resulting into more water being infiltrated into the soil. This results to a decrease in surface runoff and eventually decreased streamflow. In addition, the lower infiltration rates are associated with agricultural lands due to soil compaction and increase in soil bulk density resulting from tillage activities[22], [23].

Figure 4 shows the decadal riverflow trend. It can be observed that 1990/1991 recorded the lowest streamflow, followed by 1980/1981, then 2000/2001 and 2010/2011 seasons respectively. 2020 recorded the highest. Noticeably, there is quite a wide gap in the pattern between the 1990/1991 and the 2000/2001 streamflow and a very small

one between 2000/2001 and 2010/2011. This wide gap can be attributed to increased built-up area between 1990 and 2000. In 1990, the catchment had an area of 7.53 percent under built-up area but increased to 17.91 percent in 2000. This represents over 100 percent increase in built-up area. During this period, about 7.2 percent of the total forest and 3.4 percent of agriculture/grassland were converted to built-up area. The period between 2010 and 2020 the forest and vegetation cover experienced the highest reduction in area coverage during entire study period. Reduced vegetation/forest cover and increased built-up area exposes the soil and result to reduction in infiltration and increased run off and eventually increased streamflow.

Fig. 4: Decadal riverflow pattern from 1980-2020

Source: Field data (2021)

• Decadal Mean Streamflow and LULC Types

A correlation between streamflow and LULC type was performed in order to determine the effect of LULC on streamflow. The study revealed a significant increase in built-up area, agricultural land and indiscriminate cutting down of trees for charcoal burning. Thus, all these activities have resulted to the observed decrease in forest and vegetation cover in the catchment over the period under study.

A Correlation between forest and vegetation (FV) area and streamflow yielded a value of $r = -0.90$ ($r^2 = 81$ percent), as shown in figure 5. This is an indication of a very strong negative relationship between forest/vegetation cover and streamflow. It means that the decrease in forest/vegetation cover in the catchment has resulted to an increase in streamflow in Chalimbana River. Coefficient of determination (r^2) was 81 percent. This represents the proportion of variance in streamflow for Chalimbana River that is explained by the decrease in forest/vegetation area in the catchment.

Fig. 5: Streamflow versus forest/vegetation cover.

There is a positive relationship between streamflow and surface area of water bodies. That is, as the streamflow increases, the surface of water bodies also increases. Figure 6 shows that 71.24 percent of the change in streamflow is

influenced by the change in the area covered by water bodies whoser = 0.843.

Fig. 6: Streamflow versus Water Bodies

Based on the above analysis, the LULC changes that were observed in the catchment have had significant impact on streamflow over the study period. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is significant relationship between stream flow and changes in land-use land-cover in Chalimbana sub-catchment between 1980 and 2020 is accepted at 95 percent confidence interval. This answers the second objective which sought to establish the effects of land-use land-cover change on stream flow in the Chalimbana river catchment from 1980 to 2020.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study revealed that there has been significant land-use and land cover change in the Chalimbana sub-catchment where the forest and vegetation area covered 57.48 percent in 1980, but decreased to 28.14 percent of the catchment area in 2020. The area occupied by agriculture and grassland increased from 34.54 percent in 1980 to 56.5 percent in 2020. There was also an increase in built-up area from 7.9 percent in 1980 to 15.0 percent in 2020. The study also revealed that stream flow increased from 14.49 m³/s in 1980 to 94.4 m³/s in 2020. It was observed that the increase in built-up area as well as in agricultural activities which resulted to massive clearance of vegetation have significantly contributed to the increase in riverflow.

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